

FLAT-Net: Longitudinal Brain Graph Evolution Prediction from a Few Training Representative Templates

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Abstract. Diagnosing brain dysconnectivity disorders at an early stage amounts to understanding the evolution of such abnormal connectivities over time. Ideally, without resorting to collecting more connectomic data over time, one would predict the disease evolution with high accuracy. At this point, generative learning models from limited data can come into play to predict brain connectomic evolution over time from a single acquisition timepoint. Here, we aim to bridge the gap between data scarcity and brain connectomic evolution prediction by proposing our novel Few-shot LeArning Training Network (FLAT-Net), the *first* framework leveraging the few-shot learning paradigm for brain connectivity evolution prediction from baseline timepoint. To do so, we introduce the concept of learning from *representative connectional brain templates (CBTs)*, which encode the most centered and representative features (i.e., connectivities) for a given population of brain networks. Such CBTs capture well the data heterogeneity and diversity, hence they can train our predictive model in a frugal but generalizable manner. More specifically, our FLAT-Net starts by clustering the data into k clusters using the renowned K-means method. Then, for each cluster of *homogenous* brain networks, we create a CBT, which we call cluster specific-CBT (cs-CBT). We solely use *each cs-CBT* to train a distinct geometric generative adversarial network (gGAN) (i.e., for k clusters, we extract k cs-CBTs, and we train k gGANs (sub-model) each for a distinct cs-CBT) to learn the cs-CBT evolution over time. At the testing stage, we compute the Euclidean distance between the testing subject and each cs-CBT, and we select the gGAN model trained on the closest cs-CBT to the testing subject for prediction. A series of benchmarks against variants and excised interpretations of our framework showed that the proposed FLAT-Net, training strategy, and sub-model selection are promising strategies for predicting longitudinal brain alterations *from only a few representative templates*. Our FLAT-Net code is available at <https://github.com/basiralab/FLAT-Net>.

Keywords: brain graph evolution prediction · connectional brain template · few-shot learning · adversarial graph neural networks

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1 Introduction

Personalized treatments have become the default curative technique for many brain disorders [1]. As reported in [2], there is a correlational relationship between the quality of brain disease evolution prediction over time and the chances of patient recovery, disease reversal (e.g., mild cognitive impairment (MCI)), and healing costs reduction. As a result, a few recent studies relied on the nascent breakthroughs in machine learning techniques to predict brain connectivity evolution over time from a single timepoint [3,4].

For instance, [3] proposed Learning-Guided Infinite Network Atlas (LINAs) framework, the first graph-based machine learning method to predict the longitudinal brain network evolution from a base timepoint. Specifically, LINAs models the brain as a graph holding pairwise connectivities in-between regions of interest (ROIs). However, LINAs learning paradigm is severely dichotomized, resulting in defaulted feedback loops within its building learning blocks. To overcome this limitation, [4] proposed EvoGraphNet as a framework that leverages a graph-based Generative Adversarial Network (gGAN) [5] composed of many sequentially-trained gGANs to foresee brain graph evolution over time in an end-to-end fashion. Specifically, each gGAN aims to learn a transformation function linking a prior brain graph distribution at a timepoint t_i to its subsequent distribution at timepoint t_{i+1} . Notably, GANs are a pair of neural networks composed of a generator and a discriminator originally proposed by [6]. While the generator’s purpose is to learn how to produce imitations of the ground truth data, the discriminator’s purpose is to learn how to discriminate between the ground-truth data and the fake brain graph data produced by the generator.

With such good predictions delivered by [3] and [4], such frameworks still hold numerous limitations. For instance, these studies have only focused on predicting the longitudinal brain alterations overlooking the challenges coming with the scarcity of longitudinal neuroimaging datasets. Therefore, one can see that LINAs [3] and EvoGraphNet [4] might not deliver decent results, especially in scenarios where large datasets are not available due to the high medical image acquisition cost. As a result, these limitations raise the following question: *given a small set of training examples, how can we accurately and efficiently predict brain graph evolution over time?*

To address this question, we propose our Few-shot LeArning Training Network (FLAT-Net), a novel training and testing scheme for brain graph prediction using few representative examples. Now, it is easy to see how few-shot learning schemes are heavily prone to data heterogeneity and overfitting. Here we introduce the concept of learning from *representative connectional brain templates (CBTs)*, which encode the most centered and representative features (i.e., connectivities) for a given population of brain networks [7,5]. Such CBTs capture well the data heterogeneity and diversity, hence they can train our predictive model in a frugal but generalizable manner. To handle connectomic data heterogeneity, we first start by grouping together homogenous brain networks at baseline timepoint by clustering our dataset into k homogenous set of clusters by using the renowned K-means [8] method. Next, to reduce the effect of over-

fitting, we learn a cluster-specific CBT, which holds the most centered set of pair-wise connectivities across the cluster population at baseline timepoint. To this aim, we further extend the work of [7] to propose a Single Deep Graph Normalizer (sDGN) to map the single-view brain networks (SVBNs) of the subject population into a normalized population-representative connectional brain template (CBT). We remind the reader that a CBT [7,5] is a brain connectivity graph that selectively captures the most common pair-wise features across a population of input brain graphs (i.e., for each pair-wise connectivity, CBT captures the most common connectivities representing a population of brain graphs). We also note that, for each cluster, we extract a distinct CBT that we call cluster-specific CBT (cs-CBT), each presenting one representative template (shot) to train our model on.

Given k cs-CBTs corresponding to k clusters, we propose to train k distinct geometric deep learning frameworks each on a single cs-CBT in an end-to-end fashion. Specifically, we draw inspiration from the landmark EvoGraphNet [4] to predict the brain graph evolution over time given the longitudinal cs-CBTs as training samples. We also refer to each of the k EvoGraphNets as *sub-model*. Finally, we propose to personalize our testing phase by enhancing its prediction scheme. To do so, we propose to compute the Euclidean distance between each cs-CBT and a given baseline test connectome. Next, our FLAT-Net selects the sub-model trained on the cs-CBT that scored the lowest Euclidean distance following the assumption that the lowest Euclidean distance indicates the most suitable sub-model.

To summarize our framework, there are three main building blocks in our FLAT-Net: (i) preprocessing (i.e., clustering and cs-CBT extraction), (ii) training k geometric deep learning models, and (iii) sub-model selection. Below, we list the primary contributions of our work:

1. *On a conceptual level.* FLAT-Net is the first geometric deep learning approach that predicts brain graph evolution over time **using only a few representative training templates**.
2. *On a methodological level.* FLAT-Net is a prediction method that handles data heterogeneity as well as reduces overfitting by training a set of geometric deep learning sub-models (i.e., EvoGraphNet) using population-representative brain networks (i.e., cs-CBTs).
3. *On clinical level.* FLAT-Net can be used for clinical applications independently from the availability of a high amount of data to formalize adequate personalized treatments.

2 Proposed Method

In this section, we explain the key building steps of our proposed FLAT-Net to predict brain graph evolution over time using representative shots. **Table 1** displays the key mathematical notations used throughout this paper.

FLAT-Net overview. Here, we aim to predict brain graph evolution using a few training connectional templates. However, according to [9], it is easy

Fig. 1: Proposed three-step brain network evolution prediction framework using a few representative templates. **(I)** Data preprocessing phase. We cluster the training data to obtain k clusters using the K-Means clustering algorithm. Next, we propose sDGN to acquire normalized cluster-specific CBTs (cs-CBT). sDGN is a three-step framework: **(A)** Geometric deep learning layers. We propose a three-layer geometric deep learning network. These layers aim to learn a feature matrix V^L which consists of embeddings for each ROI. **(B)** CBT acquisition. We propose the CBT acquisition phase as a set of serial operations on the learned V^L to obtain a subject-biased CBT. For $\mathbf{V}^L = \{V_1^L, V_2^L, \dots, V_{nr}^L\}$ first, we replicate the matrix horizontally n_r times to obtain $R \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times d_i}$. Next, we compute the absolute difference of R , and its transpose R^T . Finally, we sum the result along the z-axis to estimate the final subject-biased CBT. **(C)** CBT refinement. The CBT refinement phase is proposed to eliminate the mentioned bias in cs-CBTs and accomplish a more representative cs-CBT for each cluster population. **(II)** Training phase. We propose the training scheme to generate a prediction model from our previously learned k cs-CBTs. We train k EvoGraphNet sub-models with each cs-CBT as a baseline timepoint. For each EvoGraphNet, an initial cs-CBT goes through a chain of n gGANs depending on the desired timepoint t_n to produce a graph distribution prediction at timepoint t_n . **(III)** Sub-model selection phase. We introduce the sub-model selection phase where we use Euclidean distance measurements between each cs-CBT and each testing baseline connectome to select the most appropriate sub-model for prediction.

to see how outliers can dramatically alternate the prediction course especially given that brain connectomes (i.e., graphs) are often seen as rather *unique fingerprints* for each individual. Hence, we aim to address this problem via our proposed FLAT-Net framework. To do so, we design FLAT-Net with the mindset of training with a few population-driven brain connectivity templates. We propose combining three machine-learning fundamental concepts: data preprocessing, model training, and sub-model selection, respectively. While we detail each building block separately in the following sub-sections, here, we present an overview of the need and the conduct for each step in our FLAT-Net.

The preprocessing step consists in clustering our input brain graphs into k clusters in order to segregate subject groups with similar traits. This is especially valid for few-shot learning schemes as it handles data heterogeneity [10]. First, we choose to leverage the renowned K-means clustering algorithm [11] for its reliability and to facilitate our study reproducibility. Next, for each cluster, we learn a normalized population-representative CBT, which encodes the most common and centered connectivity scheme representing the *centroid* of the clustered training population. To obtain cs-CBTs, we draw inspiration from the DGN method [7] (i.e., the current state-of-the-art study in CBT genesis). We note that, here, we adapt the original implementation to our model. We term our new implementation sDGN. We remind the reader that DGN estimates CBTs for a given population of multi-view brain networks where each view characterizes certain features of the brain structure, while sDGN uses single-view clustered brain networks for CBT generation.

Our model training consists of learning using a few representative brain templates where we train k EvoGraphNets, each on a distinct *time-dependent* cs-CBT at timepoints $\{t_i\}_{i=0}^m$. Specifically, each EvoGraphNet aims to learn how to map cs-CBT at a timepoint t_i to its following cs-CBT at timepoint t_{i+1} as shown in **Fig. 1** in an end-to-end fashion. We note that since we have k EvoGraphNets, each one is optimized for one distinct cs-CBT. Lastly, we introduce the sub-model selection step. For each testing subject at baseline timepoint t_0 , we aim to select the most suitable EvoGraphNet that guarantees the most *personalized* brain graph evolution prediction. To do so, we compute the Euclidean distance measurements between each cs-CBT and each validation data. Then, our FLAT-net decides to use the most appropriate sub-model (i.e., EvoGraphNet) based on the lowest Euclidean distance measurement. We provide in-depth details of each building block in the following sub-sections.

Data preprocessing. Given a population of n subjects, each with m brain graphs observed at m timepoints, we propose to first disentangle the baseline connectomic data heterogeneity using K-means method [11]. According to [11], K-Means clustering is the most reproducible, computationally inexpensive and accessible clustering method. Next, we leverage our adapted sDGN algorithm to learn one CBT at baseline timepoint for each cluster. We justify the choice of using cs-CBTs to train our FLAT-Net by the reliable *cluster-representativeness* offered by these CBTs. We train sDGN using a training set of SVBNs $\mathbb{X}_{\mathbf{k}} = \{\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^0, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^i, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^m\}$ for each cluster k , where $\mathbf{X}_{\mathbf{k}}^i$ denotes

the single-view brain graph tensor stacking all connectivity matrices of the cluster k at a given timepoint t_i . Each single-view brain graph tensor \mathbf{X}_k^i , passes through three geometric deep learning layers to generate the cs-CBTs at each timepoint t_i . Specifically, each layer uses an edge-conditioned filter learner [12] and is separated by ReLU non-linearity. These layers aim to learn a feature matrix $\mathbf{V}_L \in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times d_l}$ which consists of embeddings for each ROI. Following the graph convolutional layers, we obtain a subject-biased CBT by following a set of serial operations on the learned \mathbf{V}_L . However, such CBT does not fully serve our aim. Therefore, we refine these learned CBTs to eliminate the referred bias and attain a more representative cs-CBT. To do so, we compute the element-wise median of subject-biased CBTs. We propose a subject-specific normalization loss (*SNL*) to evaluate the representativeness of the generated CBT. We use a random subset of the tensor \mathbf{X}_k^i . We define our *SNL* loss for training cluster subject tr as follows:

$$\mathcal{SNL}_{n_k^s} = \sum_{i=1}^{n_k^s} \|\mathbf{T}_k - \mathbf{X}_k^i\|_F \times \lambda_{C_k} \quad (1)$$

$$\min_{W_1, b_1, \dots, W_l, b_l} \frac{1}{|\mathbf{X}_k^i|} \sum_{i=1}^{|\mathbf{T}_k|} \mathcal{SNL}_{n_k^s} \quad (2)$$

n_k^s denotes the training subject index in a cluster k where $n_k^s \in C_k$. Here C_k is the set of training subjects in cluster k . Namely, n_k denotes total number of training subjects and S is a random subset of cluster subjects. Note that we estimate the cluster-specific CBT at each timepoint t_i . The λ_{C_k} is a view specific normalization term that is defined as:

$$\lambda_{C_k} = \frac{1}{\mu_{C_k} \max \left\{ \frac{1}{\mu_j} \right\}_{j=1}^{n_k}}, \quad (3)$$

where μ_{C_k} is the mean of brain graph connectivity weights of cluster C_k and $\max \left\{ \frac{1}{\mu_j} \right\}_{j=1}^{n_k}$ is denoted as the maximum of mean reciprocals $\frac{1}{\mu_1}$ and $\frac{1}{\mu_{n_k}}$.

Proposed training scheme. We train k EvoGraphNets [4] with the previously acquired k refined cs-CBTs to successfully predict brain graph evolution from a single observation in an end-to-end fashion. Specifically, EvoGraphNet is a set of sequentially trained gGANs that aim to predict a given data distribution evolution from an initial timepoint. Each gGAN consists of two neural networks: a generator G_i and a discriminator D_i . Specifically, the generator and the discriminator collectively learn how to generate an accurate prediction of the following timepoint t_{i+1} from the previous timepoint t_i prediction obtained

Table 1: Major mathematical notations

Mathematical notation	Definition
m	total number of timepoints
n	total number of subjects
n_r	total number of regions of interest in brain
t_i	index of timepoint
C_k	set of samples in cluster k
n_k	total number of training subjects for a given cluster
k	total number of clusters
\mathbb{X}_k	baseline timepoint tensor representation $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_k \times n_r \times n_r}$ of training subjects in cluster k
\mathbf{X}_k^i	the single view brain graphs of the training population at timepoint t_n
λ_{C_k}	normalization term for SNL loss
μ_{C_k}	the mean of graph connectivity weights of cluster C_k
μ_k	mean of the connected edge weights for node k in a ground-truth brain graph
σ_k	standard deviation of the connected edge weights for node k in a ground-truth brain graph
$\hat{\mu}_k$	mean of the connected edge weights for node k in a predicted brain graph
$\hat{\sigma}_k$	standard deviation of the connected edge weights for node k in a predicted brain graph
p_k	normal distribution of the connected edge weights for a node k in a ground-truth brain graph
\tilde{p}_k	normal distribution of the connected edge weights for a node k in the ground truth brain graph
\mathbf{T}_i^k	ground-truth training cs-CBT $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$ at t_i
$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_i^k$	predicted cs-CBT $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$ at t_i
$\mathbf{X}_{t_i}^{st}$	brain graph connectivity matrices $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$ of test data at t_i
G_i	GAN generator at timepoint t_i
D_i	GAN discriminator at timepoint t_i
\mathcal{L}_{full}	full loss function
\mathcal{L}_{adv}	adversarial loss function
\mathcal{L}_{L_1}	l_1 loss function
\mathcal{L}_{KL}	KL divergence loss function
λ_1	coefficient of adversarial loss
λ_2	coefficient of l_1 loss
λ_3	coefficient of KL divergence loss
\mathbf{V}_L	learned attributes matrix $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times d_t}$
T_k	set of cs-CBTs
\mathbb{X}_k	baseline timepoint tensor representation $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_k \times n_r \times n_r}$ of training subjects in cluster k
\mathbf{X}_k^i	the single view brain graphs of the training population at timepoint t_n
λ_{C_k}	normalization term for SNL loss
μ_{C_k}	the mean of graph connectivity weights of cluster C_k
μ_k	mean of the connected edge weights for node k in a ground-truth brain graph
σ_k	standard deviation of the connected edge weights for node k in a ground-truth brain graph
$\hat{\mu}_k$	mean of the connected edge weights for node k in a predicted brain graph
$\hat{\sigma}_k$	standard deviation of the connected edge weights for node k in a predicted brain graph
p_k	normal distribution of the connected edge weights for a node k in a ground-truth brain graph
\tilde{p}_k	normal distribution of the connected edge weights for a node k in the ground truth brain graph
\mathbf{T}_i^k	ground-truth training cs-CBT $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$ at t_i
$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_i^k$	predicted cs-CBT $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$ at t_i
$\mathbf{X}_{t_i}^{st}$	brain graph connectivity matrices $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r}$ of test data at t_i
G_i	GAN generator at timepoint t_i
D_i	GAN discriminator at timepoint t_i
\mathcal{L}_{full}	full loss function
\mathcal{L}_{adv}	adversarial loss function
\mathcal{L}_{L_1}	l_1 loss function
\mathcal{L}_{KL}	KL divergence loss function
λ_1	coefficient of adversarial loss
λ_2	coefficient of l_1 loss
λ_3	coefficient of KL divergence loss
\mathbf{V}_L	learned attributes matrix $\in \mathbb{R}^{n_r \times n_r \times d_t}$
T_k	set of cs-CBTs

by the preceding gGAN. Below is the adversarial loss function for one pair of generator G_i and discriminator D_i composing an elementary gGAN at a given timepoint t_i :

$$\operatorname{argmin}_{G_i} \max_{D_i} \mathcal{L}_{adv}(G_i, D_i) = \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{T}^k} [\log D_i(\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k)] + \mathbb{E}_{\mathbf{T}^k} [\log(1 - D_i(G_i(\mathbf{T}_{t_{i-1}}^k)))] \quad (4)$$

$\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_{i-1}}^k$ denotes the predicted cs-CBT by a subsequent generator G_{i-1} at timepoint t_{i-1} . The generator G_i takes $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_{i-1}}^k$ as an input and aims learn how to generate a prediction of $\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k$, the ground-truth brain connectivity matrix for a timepoint t_i . The discriminator D_i takes the prediction $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_i}^k$ produced by the generator G_i , and the ground-truth data $\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k$ to learn how to better differentiate between ground-truth cs-CBT and the predicted cs-CBT.

Since we expect the brain connectivity alterations to be sparse over time, we hypothesize that the l_1 distance between successive timepoints t_{i-1} and t_i is considerably small. Therefore, in addition to the adversarial loss, we add l_1 loss to further minimize the distance between $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_{i-1}}^k$ and $\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k$. Below is the l_1 loss function for each template (i.e., cs-CBT) \mathbf{T}_k for an elementary timepoint t_i :

$$\mathcal{L}_{l1}(G_i, \mathbf{T}_k) = \|\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_{i-1}}^k - \mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k\|_1 \quad (5)$$

In addition to l_1 loss, we propose to use KL -divergence loss to eliminate the inconsistency between ground-truth $\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k$ and the predicted $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_i}^k$ connectivity weight distributions. To compute our KL loss, we first calculate the mean μ_k and the standard deviation σ_k of connected edge weights for each ROI in in ground-truth cs-CBT $\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k$. We define p_k as the normal distribution for the node k in the ground-truth cs-CBT $\mathbf{T}_{t_i}^k$. Then, we calculate the mean $\hat{\mu}_k$ and the standard deviation $\hat{\sigma}_k$ of connected edge weights for each ROI in the predicted cs-CBT $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_i}^k$. We define q_k as the normal distribution for the same node k in the predicted cs-CBT $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_{t_i}^k$. Below is the normal distributions expression:

$$p_k = N(\mu_k, \sigma_k), \quad (6)$$

$$q_k = N(\hat{\mu}_k, \hat{\sigma}_k) \quad (7)$$

The KL -divergence between the previously calculated normal distributions p_k and q_k for each cs-CBT \mathbf{T}_k is expressed as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{KL} = \sum_{k=1}^{n_r} KL(q_k || p_k), \quad (8)$$

Namely, each node k 's KL divergence is expressed as:

$$KL(q_k||p_k) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} q_k(x) \log \frac{q_k(x)}{p_k(x)} dx \quad (9)$$

Eventually, we obtain the full loss function to optimize by adding all the above-mentioned loss functions as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{Full} = \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\lambda_1 \mathcal{L}_{adv}(G_i, D_i) + \lambda_2 \mathcal{L}_{l1}(G_i, \mathbf{T}_i^k) + \lambda_3 \mathcal{L}_{KL} \right) \quad (10)$$

λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 are hyperparameters controlling the influence of each loss function in the overall purpose.

Sub-model selection. Our testing strategy consists of selecting the most appropriate sub-model (i.e., trained EvoGraphNet) for a given testing subject. To do so, we calculate the Euclidean distances between each cs-CBT \mathbf{T}_k , and the ground-truth test data $\mathbf{X}_{t_i}^{tst}$ for each timepoint t_i . Then, we choose the sub-model trained for the cs-CBT \mathbf{T}_k having the lowest distance to ground-truth test data $\mathbf{X}_{t_i}^{tst}$. Below we express, the absolute difference function to successfully choose the most compatible method:

$$\mathcal{D}(\mathbf{X}_{t_i}^{tst}, \mathbf{T}_k) = \|\mathbf{X}_{t_i}^{tst} - \mathbf{T}_k\|_1 \quad (11)$$

Next, we used the selected sub-model to predict the follow-up connectomes $\{t_i\}_{i=1}^m$ for the baseline testing connectome at t_0 .

3 Results and Discussion

Evaluation dataset. We used 58 subjects from the OASIS-21 longitudinal dataset [13]. This set consists of a longitudinal collection of 150 subjects aged 60 to 96. Each subject was scanned on two visits, separated by at least one year. We construct a cortical morphological network for each subject derived from cortical thickness measurement using structural T1-w MRI as proposed in [14,15]. The left cortical hemispheres are parcellated into 35 ROIs using Desikan-Killiany cortical atlas [16] for the given dataset. For our evaluation, we use the cortical morphological networks to predict brain network evolution for two consecutive timepoints t_1 and t_2 from a baseline observation t_0 . We built our geometric deep learning layer architecture for sDGN, and gGAN architecture for EvoGraphNet with the PyTorch Geometric library.

Parameter setting. In Table 2, we report the averaged prediction mean absolute error (MAE) and best MAE. In addition, in Table 3 we report the

node strength [17] and eigenvector centrality [17]. For preprocessing, we set the number of clusters k to 3. For sDGN, we fixed the geometric deep learning layer output embeddings to 36, 24, and 5, consecutively. We note that each layer is followed by the ReLU activation function. All models are trained using Adam optimizer [18]. Specifically, we set our optimizer learning rate to 0.0005. The number of random samples in our SNL function is fixed to 10. The sDGN is trained for 300 epochs with 3-fold cross-validation. For training, we set each pair of gGAN hyperparameters as follows: $\lambda_1 = 2$, $\lambda_2 = 2$, and $\lambda_3 = 0.001$. Also, we chose AdamW [18] as our default optimizer. To do so, we set the exponential decay rate for the first moment estimates (i.e., beta 1) to 0.5, and the exponential decay rate for the second-moment estimates (i.e., beta 2) to 0.999 for the AdamW optimizer [18]. We set the learning rate of the optimizer as 0.01 for each generator and as 0.0002 for each discriminator. Finally, we trained our sub-models (i.e., EvoGraphNets) for 300 epochs using a single Tesla V100 GPU (NVIDIA GeForce GTX TITAN with 32GB memory).

Comparison Methods and evaluation. To evaluate the reliability of our FLAT-Net, we used a 3-fold cross-validation strategy for training and testing. Since there are no other existing works on few-shot learning brain graph evaluation prediction, we proposed to assess our method against three ablated approaches. For the first comparison method: FLAT-Net (w/o clustering), we simplified the preprocessing phase to observe the influence of our proposed clustering method on overall FLAT-Net performance. To do so, we eliminated the clustering operation and used solely our proposed sDGN to obtain one CBT of the training dataset at each timepoint independently. Specifically, the training is completed by using the longitudinal CBT to train one EvoGraphNet model. The second comparison method: FLAT-Net (w/o sub-model selection), we removed the sub-model selection phase and used one model for testing to evaluate the impact of our proposed sub-model selection process on overall FLAT-Net performance. Particularly, we create an average model by simply averaging the weights of sub-models learned by training of k cluster-specific EvoGraphNets at each follow-up timepoint independently. In the final comparison method FLAT-Net (w hierarchical clustering), we evaluated a different clustering approach. Basically, we used hierarchical clustering [19] in the preprocessing step prior to the model training.

Table 2: Prediction accuracy using mean absolute error (MAE) and best MAE of our proposed method and comparison methods at t_1 and t_2 timepoints.

Method	t_1		t_2	
	Mean MAE ± std	Best MAE	Mean MAE ± std	Best MAE
FLAT-Net (w/o clustering+w/o sub-model selection)	0.06559 ± 0.0005705	0.06621	0.06764 ± 0.0000381	0.06769
FLAT-Net(w/o sub-model selection)	0.06509 ± 0.0004667	0.06557	0.06555 ± 0.0002728	0.06593
FLAT-Net(w hierarchical clustering)	0.60295 ± 0.0003447	0.06076	0.0652 ± 0.00005244	0.065281
FLAT-Net	0.05687 ± 0.0008025	0.057631	0.06021 ± 0.0002091	0.060499

Table 3: Prediction accuracy using node centrality and eigenvector centrality mean absolute error (MAE) of our proposed method and comparison methods at t_1 and t_2 timepoints. FLAT-Net: Longitudinal Brain Graph Prediction 11

Method	t_1		t_2	
	Node Strength MAE	Eigenvector Centrality MAE	Node Strength MAE	Eigenvector Centrality MAE
FLAT-Net (w/o clustering+w/o sub-model selection)	1.01825	0.029177	1.146202	0.033098
FLAT-Net(w/o sub-model selection)	0.952191	0.024133	1.252288	0.031682
FLAT-Net(w hierarchical clustering)	1.056528	0.03066	1.195618	0.03361
FLAT-Net	0.772809	0.025313	1.076591	0.033308

Table 2 shows that our proposed framework outperformed each comparison method in terms of mean MAE (averaged across 3 folds) and in terms of the best MAE for prediction at t_1 and t_2 . In other words, using our few representative training templates, our FLAT-Net reduces the risk of model divergence caused by outliers. Our proposed framework achieved the minimum mean MAE in terms of node strength [17] (averaged across 3 folds) for both t_1 and t_2 in comparison with other methods. Particularly, node strength is a powerful indicator for analyzing the brain longitudinal evolution in both healthy and disordered brain networks. Alterations in node strength might be explained by the progression of undesired neurodegenerative diseases such as Alzheimers disease [20]. However, our proposed framework could not display the best performance in terms of the mean eigenvector centrality (averaged across 3 folds). An increase in eigenvector centrality might be due to the fact that our proposed sDGN has a centralization effect making the framework less prone to recognizing localized differences between brain graph populations [21]. Overall, our proposed FLAT-Net achieved the best performance in terms of mean MAE, best MAE, and node strength mean MAE in comparison to benchmark methods and its variants (e.g., using hierarchical clustering). Thus, to some extent one can confirm that our method is reliable to simultaneously provide a precision diagnosis to patients regardless of the amount of the input data.

Limitations and future work. Despite the good performance displayed by our FLAT-Net, it has a few limitations. So far, our FLAT-Net only operates on single-edge connections between brain ROIs. Therefore, in future work, we aim to fully represent the complexity of the brain with distinct topological attributes. To do so, we further aim to generalize our proposed preprocessing, training, and sub-model selection phases to handle hypergraphs. Specifically, hypergraphs consist of hyperedges (i.e., high-order connections) between each ROI that captures the high-order relationships. Furthermore, we notice that the inclusion of the sub-model selection phase produced a considerable advancement in the longitudinal brain graph evolution prediction with few-shot learning. Consequently, in our future work, we aim to optimize the sub-model selection phase.

4 Conclusion

In this paper, we propose a novel brain graph evolution prediction framework using a few representative shots. Our FLAT-Net comprises three steps: preprocessing, training, and sub-model selection. We clustered the training data into a set of k clusters to overcome the prediction errors caused by outliers and to handle data heterogeneity. By learning a population-driven connectional template for each cluster and at each timepoint, we train an EvoGraphNet using each

connectional template evolution trajectory. For trajectory inference, we select the EvoGraphNet trained on the cluster-specific CBT that is most similar to the given testing connectome at baseline timepoint t_0 . Our results showed that FLAT-Net could remarkably improve the prediction accuracy compared to its excised variants. Our FLAT-Net can be used to predict both typical and disordered brain evolution trajectories using a few training brain samples. In our future research, we aim to investigate the prediction accuracy of our FLAT-Net on multimodal brain graphs where the relationship between two brain regions is captured by multiple edge weights (e.g., neural correlation and morphological dissimilarity).

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6 Supplementary material

We provide three supplementary items for reproducible and open science:

1. A 5-min YouTube video explaining how our framework works on BASIRA YouTube channel at <https://youtu.be/cD74q7qcI-4>.
2. FLAT-Net code in Python on GitHub at <https://github.com/basiralab/FLAT-Net>.
3. A GitHub video code demo on BASIRA YouTube channel at https://youtu.be/Q8RWv01j_PI.

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